

Enhancement of liner materials based on nanomaterials to promote sustainability in noise intercourse

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Article Info

Article history:

Received May 18, 2024

Revised Aug 27, 2024

Accepted Sep 17, 2024

Keywords:

3D-IC integration

Aggressive TSV

Future IC integration

Noise intercourse

TSV

ABSTRACT

Daily usage of devices has had a major influence on lives and existence, which would be unimaginable without them. Due to this, recent gadget dependability concerns need particular attention. PCs, hand mobile phones, and other computerized household gadgets need integrated circuits (ICs). Individual components must work together to accomplish their tasks and make the circuit operate. Hot carrier effect, oxide breakdown, and other system-level problems result from accommodating several devices in a planar IC. Vertical linking active components in one IC to another IC is a common method of three-dimensional IC integration (3D-IC). The main issue with 3D-IC adoption is electrical interference to neighboring through silicon via (TSV) and active transistors, which substantially reduces system performance. The electrical TSV (ETSV) model, which employs solely electrical signal carrying TSV, and the thermal TSV (TTSV) model, which incorporates thermal TSV during simulation, are used in this research to reduce electrical interference. The electrical signal transporting TSV to the substrate and other TSV was investigated for interference. With other models, this study also shows higher frequency regimes up to 1 THz. We found that the suggested methodology improves 3D-IC development by more than 30% by reducing electrical interference from signal-carrying TSV to other TSV.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Increase the number of transistors inside a single integrated circuit (IC) by artificially or genuinely adjusting the outside of a round single-precious stone Si called the substrate. The IC's construct zone is described as a bite the dust. To reduce manufacturing costs, a large number of die are prepared on a single substrate and thus dice. When one die is bundled together, it is referred to as a chip. A single gem Si wafers are commonly used as the foundation of ICs. The fundamental procedures used to construct an IC are as follows: Testimony is only a concoction or physical statement form that has been acclimated to store a material film onto a substrate. Etching is defined as completed when a fabric or materials from the surface must be removed. The etching procedure works specifically by covering surface areas that need to be protected. Ion Implantation was a technique used to introduce dopant debasements into a wafer. An electrical field is used to acclimate quicken ionized particles into a specific wafer zone. This technique is used to transfer geometric forms to the outside of the wafer by donating patterns with a veil.

Because Moore's law continuously reduces device lengths, IC recital has improved over the past 40 years. In the accurate scaling era, ICs have mostly operated on a planar substrate. In recent years, two additional challenges have surfaced. The first is that there has been a regression in the scaling of device dimensions. The underlying issue is that interconnect display restricts the total presentation of the system. The real restriction has been identified as the interconnect disruption, which is almost indistinguishable from the device delay. Modern structures and new connecting materials need to be developed in order to meet system performance requirements. To cut down on interconnect delays, new integration strategies have been devised [1], [2].

As a result, three-dimensional IC (3D-ICs) are one of the best platforms for these heterogeneous applications. Due to 3D integration technology stacking numerous layers of devices with high-thickness interconnects between them, it is feasible diligencing for CMOS applications. One significant benefit of 3D-IC is its capacity for heterogeneous integration. Several stacking techniques are used to achieve 3D integration [3]–[6]. In addition to 3D-IC, new devices are required [7]–[9] to significantly improve system efficiency. A vast array of emerging technologies and processes are required within a single system. As a result, 3D ICs are one of the best platforms for these heterogeneous applications.

A vast array of emerging technologies and processes are required within a single system. As a result, 3D-ICs are one of the best platforms for these heterogeneous applications. To realize the full potential of the 3D platform, the intriguing issues identified with 3D-ICs must be resolved. This paper considers a few key obstacles in 3D-ICs at various abstraction levels, ranging from devices to structure methodologies. Electrical and thermal models for the interface between through-substrate-via's (TSV's) are invented in this 3D-IC structure. TSVs can be used to enable the 3-D gateway, but they will raise new issues. Noise intercourse between TSV and substrate is measured inside heterogeneous 3D-ICs. To identify and mitigate substrate intercourse issues, various models, materials, and circuit techniques are proposed. This paper introduces a novel method for reducing electrical interference in TSV structures by using different dielectric materials as the liner. And employs three distinct models using various dielectric materials such as Perylene and Teflon. The proposed architecture was also investigated at extremely high frequencies of up to THz.

3DIC integration faces many challenges, including limitations in the fabrication procedure, failures, and noise intercourse problems [10], [11]. The main problem with 3D-IC is noise intercourse from TSV to active circuit. By verifying the intercourse of TSV and LC-voltage control oscillator, as well as TSV to PMOS body and TSV to NMOS body, this work explores noise intercourse. TSV will be linked next to LC-VCO, and since LC-VCO contains the bodies of PMOS and NMOS, noise will swiftly go from the substrate to the bodies of PMOS and NMOS.

To lessen noise intercourse in 3D-IC, a planar inductor and an integrated solenoid inductor are employed [12], [13]. Two stacked dies are employed. A signal that mimics a high-speed digital clock, a key element of a digital block and a powerful adversary of analog circuits, is present in the bottom die. Two distinct integrated inductor structures are created above these clock signal lines; the traditional planar inductor is employed as a reference layout, and a higher solenoid inductor is introduced for noise reduction.

TSV based 3D-ICs have been proposed to use a low-power and dependable clock network design. It was investigated how the TSV count affected the TSV effective resistance-capacitance effect of the clock [14]. The effects of TSV noise intercourse on the power supply network in 3D-ICs were analyzed and modeled using MTL. The operating bandwidth of high density TSVs is increased, but the electromagnetic intercourse impact increases [15]. It was suggested [16] to analyze the mechanical stress and electrical noise intercourse caused by TSV in sub 5-nm node nanosheet FETs for heterogeneous 3D-ICs. Through silicon via with guard ring is the most significant choice to improve the electrical signal interference [17] but guard rings take extra area which in turn reduces the system performance. Numerical analysis of TSV's were studied with different mechanism like inverse Laplace [18]–[22]. Furthermore, noise intercourse study between active device to TSV was studied at RF frequency range [23]–[27].

The objective of the current work is to diminish electrical flag obstructions by utilizing the suitable dielectric fabric as an forceful TSV liner and with different structures, such as TTSV, ETSV, and ETSV with a warm source. Also, diverse liner materials were utilized to consider clamor Intercut effectiveness rather than conventional SiO₂. This ponder moreover centers on the dielectric and fitting center fabric combination, which brings down electrical obstructions between forceful TSV (ETSV) and casualty TSV whereas at the same time expanding the conductivity of the flag carrying TSV. For the proposed structures, we have chosen CMOS congruous fabric.

2. SIMULATION CONFIGURATION TO STUDY NOISE INTERCOURSE IN 3D-IC

The fewer interconnects and thus lower load capacitance in 3D-ICs will reduce the commotion caused by simultaneous exchanging occasions. Because shorter wires have lower capacitance, there will be less noise between signal lines. Shorter wires with fewer repeaters should also have less commotion and

jitter, resulting in better signal integrity. Because 3D-IC has a lower wiring load, it is possible to drive a greater number of gates. Density is measured in three dimensions, dynamic devices are frequently stacked, and the size of a chip impression is regularly reduced. This gave the standard two-dimensional device a third dimension.

To diminish electrical impedances, different dielectric materials based on their properties are presented into each TSV's show and the comes about are examined. The clamor Intercut show for 3D-IC is delineated in Figure 1. The show comprises of a single layer IC with four TSVs to explore flag keenness. Electrical impedances was moreover examined utilizing different stacked IC squares, as appeared in Figure 2.

Measuring from the signal carrying TSV to the other TSV yields the dimensions of 3D-IC. Every TSV's diameter was measured at 2 μm . The pitch between two TSVs (the shortest path between the centers of both adjacent TSVs) is anticipated to be 2 μm , per the international technology roadmap for semiconductors (ITRS). We have utilized COMSOL multiphysics' FEM simulator to investigate electrical interference.

Figure 1. Top view of single IC electrical model Figure 2. Prototype of noise intercourse simulation

Silicon (Si) is the most used substrate material because it is less expensive than other materials and is used for memory and processor applications. The common circuit employs various dielectric materials. The resistivity and dielectric constant of each material are important parameters in the noise intercourse analysis. Individual noise intercourse is thus investigated using these dielectric materials.

3. LINER MATERIAL OPTIMIZATION

Stacking of devices from one IC to another IC vertically overcomes the scaling issues and keep on track Moore's law further as predicted in every one-year number of devices double per chip. Also desire of low-cost high-speed devices made transistor size further reduced, but semiconductor industries already hit back to the extreme. 3D-IC is one of the emerging technologies which not only helped the semiconductor manufacturing companies but also keep on track the Moore's law. In 3D-IC stacking of IC's vertically and electrically connected through TSV's. Noise intercourse is one of the major issues during integration where in active devices get turned on automatically if threshold voltage is smaller than the interference voltage. Hence, liner material plays an important role to resist the noise intercourse. Optimization and choose of proper dielectric liner material surrounding TSV is an important role prior to integration. Liner material must be a CMOS compatible and can able to deposit with standard chemical vapour deposition process. In the current we have chosen various liner materials like air, silicon dioxide, Hafnium oxide, Teflon, Perylene-N, benzocyclobutene (BCB). Also, the liner thickness plays an important role. In the proposed model we have used standard ITRS road map thickness of 150 nm. Dielectric constant of SiO₂ is higher than all.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The desire for minimal, multi-purpose, superior hardware has resulted in a significant increase in the office thickness of gadgets. Warm dispersal per chip territory and per volume of framework walled in area has grown greatly in the latest decade. To make matters worse, framework level requirements for small gadgets frequently incorporate low skin temperatures and negligible or no vent openings, as well as

limitations to throttling, which will negatively influence execution. The continued reduction of lithographic scales at the IC level implies that size sizes of 45-30 nm are now normal. However, every decrease in these scales is additionally associated with exponentially higher spillage power, making warm dissemination increasingly difficult. 3D-IC is most widely used technique adopted by semiconductor industries to accommodate many devices without scaling it. Hence the transistor level disadvantages like hot carrier effect, and short channel effect can be irradiated.

To reduce unwanted sound in 3D-IC integration, various models are utilized in multiple ICs. Transmitting electric signal between 3D ICs and other active devices requires TSVs. The main downside is the interference between neighboring TSVs and the electrical TSVs for signaling. This study demonstrates the enhancement of electrical interference from TSV to substrate and TSV-to-TSV by changing the dielectric materials in different liner structures. The research uses thermal through silicon vias (TTSV), electrical through silicon vias (ETSV), and a heat source to investigate electrical crosstalk. The examination is conducted at various parameters, including high frequencies and electrical signaling.

Frequency response analysis aids in estimating the noise interference model and recommends diverse noise isolation methods. The frequency response model is simulated using an FEM simulator, covering frequencies from low to high range (1 KHz-1 THz). The simulation employs materials with similar electrical characteristics like SiO₂, BCB, Teflon, and Perylene for frequency analysis. In Figure 3, the ETSV model depicts the noise interference analysis. Figure 4 illustrates the noise interference analysis for the heat source model combined with the ETSV model, applying a power of 1 MW. Additionally, Figure 5 shows the noise interference analysis along with the TTSV model. Controlling temperature is crucial for 3D-IC integration to ensure efficient heat dissipation and prevent adverse effects on active devices, thereby maintaining optimal system performance.

Figure 3. Noise intercourse study

Figure 4. Noise intercourse study including heat source

Figure 5. Noise intercourse study for TTSV model

Besides, ETSV shows with diverse dielectric fabrics were considered. CMOS is congruous and the materials can be kept utilizing routine chemical vapor deposition (CVD) strategies are chosen like SiO₂, BCB, Teflon AF1600, and Perylene-N as liner fabric. Liner confines the TSV and the Silicon substrate. As portrayed in Figure 6 convectional SiO₂ liner has fewer electrical impedances from flag-carrying TSV to casualty TSV compared to other Re-enacted liner materials. Moreover, electrical obstructions were considered indeed flag-carrying TSV with exceptionally tall recurrence extending up to THz. Teflon liner fabric has significantly more obstructions from flag-carrying TSV to casualty TSV compared to other liner materials re-enacted with ETSV show as portrayed in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Noise intercourse study using different dielectric materials using ETSV model

Figure 7. Noise intercourse study at very high frequency up to 1 THz using different dielectric materials for the ETSV model

4.1. Noise coupling study using guard rings

Teflon AF1600 liner is used to demonstrate the noise coupling performance for a variety of TSV topologies, including liner alone and liner encircled by a p⁺ guard ring. For electrical interference even the topologies have been evaluated with and without guard ring. Figure 8 shows the noise coupling study using liner material only. Figure 9 illustrates the noise coupling study using liner as well as p⁺ guard ring.

At the victim TSV, comparatively minimal noise coupling was noted using Teflon AF1600 liner material with a P⁺ guard ring as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8. Noise coupling study using liner only

Figure 9. Noise coupling study using liner and guard ring

Figure 10. Electrical interference with and without guard ring

5. CONCLUSION

Numerous technical advancements have been developed in order to facilitate the development of IC. Devices are used on a regular basis, and as a consequence, they have had a significant influence on the lives and existence of individuals on a scale that would be incomprehensible in the absence of these devices. As a consequence of this, the dependability difficulties that are associated with relatively new gadgets call for unusual and specialized effort. Therefore, it can be deduced that 3D-IC will act as a stage for all of these different kinds of frameworks since it is anticipated that a broad range of growing technologies, processes, and materials would co-exist inside a single framework. In this study, a variety of significant challenges in 3D-IC are discussed at many levels. These challenges vary from the development of new devices to the development of innovative methodologies that may improve system performance while simultaneously reducing chip size and range. In this study, unique models seem to be developed in order to reduce electrical impedances in combination with various dielectric materials. In addition to that, impedance models were investigated for a variety of dielectric materials, and they were tested at very high frequencies up to one terahertz. Teflon liner fabric has been shown to have an extraordinarily high resistance to impedances at high frequency administration, as well as a reduction in obstructions of up to thirty percent of functioning IC integration, according to our findings. An investigation into a variety of core materials, an examination of a variety of liner materials, and the use of a variety of TSV models are all potential approaches to further reduce noise interaction.

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